

Bacterial Pigments as Natural Alternatives to Antibiotics by Inhibition Mechanisms and Their Applications in Combating Microbial Resistance: A Review

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Abstract

Bacteria produce natural pigment or dye this dye called bacterial pigments, these are composed from chemical substances that have important biological activities. Bacteria can be a good alternative source for synthetic vital pigment also bacteria pigment have a better biodegradability and high compatibility with environment. Bacteria like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptomyces*, *Nocardia* and other bacteria make the dyes like a virulence factor. These pigments are of different colors, such as red, yellow, orange, green, and black. They are of great importance in that they act as antioxidants, antituberculosis and anticancer agents in the textile and food industries. The discovery and development of new antibiotics are crucial due to the increasing threat of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The biosafety properties of bacterial pigments make them an integral part of pharmaceuticals preparation, and this is not limited to medicine also used in industry and biotechnology. In recent years bacteria may be resistant to all antibiotics and have become clear threat to community in general with increase deaths resulting from bacterial infections.

Keywords: *Bacterial pigments, biological activity, bacteria, chemical structure, antibiotics.*

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Introduction

Bacteria are a microorganisms that are found in nature since ancient time and this due to ability to stay at live in the most difficult circumstances ,it found in seas ,oceans, lakes, swamps, rivers, hot springs oil wells, soil ,air, tree and fresh water and this it give important roles to produce pigment in numerous colors it is called Bacterial pigments (Meng et al., 2022). Bacterial pigments a terms that refers to chemical substances with have good diverse properties against many medical cases like infections oxidative, inflammatory, infections, ultra violet(U V) protection and cancer disease (Agarwal et al., 2023).These features make it not a minor metabolic product under exhausting condition but rather it can be used in many biomedical fields and applications in the pharmaceutical preparations and food as well as cosmetics industries, Bacteria grown in different geographical regions with different temperatures enabled to

tolerate extreme conditions, as a result these pigments of multiple colors were formed to protect themselves (Azman et al., 2018). Prior to the development of synthetic dyes in 1856 by Perkin, natural pigments were widely used and constituted a great part of world trade and prosperity. Because of their potential industrial and biomedical applications (Chatragadda & Dufossé, 2021), microbial pigments have recently become the subject of intensive research. On the other hand, a large number of synthetic pigment dyes are non-biodegradable and have considerable environmental hazards. Additionally, synthetic colorants are toxic and carcinogenic that could raise concern of possible effect on human health (Grewal et al., 2022). Bacteria are free living organisms found throughout nature, some of them live normally in the human intestine and make substances like vitamins and fatty acid by breaking down wastes that are utility to human body (Husnik et al., 2021). Bacteria form complex structures such as hyphae, and molds make pigments such as melanin, prodigiosin, pyocyanin, violacein, bacteriochlorophylls, carotenoids, and monascins (Ursan et al., 2019; Boonmahome & Mongkolthanaruk, 2023). Bacterial infections remain a critical issue to humans due to quick spread and high mutation rates of bacteria, they eventually become resistant against traditional antibiotics. Financial Burden Antimicrobial resistance is a major public health problem, because it interferes with infection control and presents an economic burden. There is therefore a growing scientific interest in alternative and innovative forces among which, the use of bacterial pigments Can be one of means to combat the ever growing problem of multidrug resistant pathogens (Stankovic et al., 2012). Several bacterial species, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Sarcina maxima*, *Micrococcus roseus*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Shewanella colwelliana*, *Streptomyces* spp., and *Bacillus* spp., are capable of producing a wide range of pigments that differ in color and biological activity and can be isolated from diverse environmental sources. Microorganisms synthesize various classes of pigments, such as carotenoids, melanins, quinones, flavins, monascins, prodigiosins, violacein, and indigo (Rokade & Pethe, 2016). Pigment production is strongly influenced by multiple factors, including carbon and nitrogen sources, pH, temperature, incubation time, moisture content, and aeration rate. Therefore, optimizing growth conditions is essential to enhance both the yield and quality of bacterial pigments (Celedón & Díaz, 2021). Bacterial pigments have a good qualities and the genetic engineering techniques have proven to be highly active in a value effective manner and can sifting and diagnostic strains with high pigment yields (Numan et al., 2018). In some cases, pigments of bacteria may serve as a defense and thus, become natural antimicrobial substances against other rival microorganisms. In some environments pigments are involved in capturing nutrients; For instance, in cyanobacteria substances called pigments are used to produce energy. Many bacterial pigments have been shown to have antimicrobial growth inhibitory effects on other bacteria, therefore acting as a mechanism for eliminating competitors for space and resources (Dehbashi et al., 2021). Fluorescent bacterial pigments are further utilized in the laboratory, such as in labeling antibodies and observing the course of certain biochemical reactions. Photosynthetic bacteria use pigments as chlorophyll in photosynthesis. Therefore, the objectives of the present study were to isolating pigment-producing microorganisms, develop a simple and high-yield method for producing commercial pigments with selected strains, and optimize the influencing factors on pigment biosynthesis.

Microbial Pigments

Microorganisms such as bacteria gram positive or negative ,fungi and algae are ability to produced microbial pigments, Microbial pigments are usually sen in two forms as pigments diffused out in the media and pigments retained within the cells, The most commonly studied microbial pigments include carotenoids, anthocyanin, and flavonoids, each with distinct chemical properties and biological activities. (Barreto et al., 2023). The cold-adapted microorganisms produce various pigments as secondary metabolites under changing physiological conditions, stresses due to environment and to survive. Studies performed at glacial and high altitude regions have found a significantly higher per cent of pigment-forming bacteria (Saini et al., 2020; Silva et al., 2021). These pigments which are synthesized by microbial

microorganisms, play various biological roles such as; survival and adaptation to the environment, protection from ultraviolet radiation and reactive oxygen species, as well as antibacterial activity and anti-fungi (helps them to be dominant in territory / but we can impede growth of competing microorganism on nutrient). Furthermore, some of the pigments are involved in photosynthesis and thus can support energy generation at the cellular level (Shen et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2017; Aruldass et al., 2018). Pigment-producing bacteria Stains of pigment-formed organisms can be generally split into two types, true marine strains and environment adaptable strains (Jeong et al., 2022). In addition, microbial pigments have important nutritional and therapeutic value (Sen et al., 2019). The functions of pigments in living organisms range from external such as visual signalization and attraction to internal vital physiological processes (Gahlawat & Choudhury, 2019). Microbial pigments represent characteristic features of certain bacterial species and can serve as valuable markers for microbial identification, as pigmented bacteria form colonies exhibiting distinct coloration. Depending on the microorganism, these pigments may be produced either intracellularly or extracellularly, and they fulfill diverse physicochemical and ecological roles (Chatragadda & Dufossé, 2021). Most bacterial pigments are insoluble in water but can be selectively extracted using organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, or hexane. Following extraction, the organic solvent is allowed to evaporate, leaving behind a powdered residue that represents purified pigment suitable for functional and biological analyses (Mumtaz et al., 2019). Pigments constitute important organic components of the bacterial protoplasm and include compounds such as melanin, prodigiosin, iodinine, pyocyanin, violacein, and phenazines. These pigments have been isolated from bacterial species including *Serratia phymuthica*, *Serratia rubidaea*, *Habella chejuensis*, and *Vibrio gazogenes*, and several studies have reported their notable antifungal and antibacterial activities (Pratik et al., 2019).

Pigment-Producing Bacteria

Staphylococcus Species

Several *Staphylococcus* species produce high levels of membrane-associated pigments associated with the protection against adverse environmental conditions. These pigments are composed of carotenoids, melanin and staphyloxanthin and have a potential for use in food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries (Nurjahan et al., 2020). *Staphylococcus aureus* is usually seen in grape like clusters because it divides in several planes. This generates a golden pigment that provides the cells with their characteristic color and is also an important virulence factor. Moreover, the surface of *S. aureus* is decorated with several adhesin proteins linked via covalent bonds to the peptidoglycan which enable the microbe not only to adhere to host tissues but also enhance its pathogenicity, virulence factors are molecules that assist the bacterium in establishing an infection, damaging the host and interfering with host immunity, the regulation of important virulence factors also increase the risk of invasive and recurrent *S. aureus* infections (Rowe et al., 2021). The vital pigment one of the defensive lines against another pathogenic bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* possesses a specific virulence factor called coagulase, It can be detected by coagulase test. which plays a significant role in biofilms formation during *S. aureus* infections, this is help in effective antibiotics resistant, *S. aureus* enable the cell to penetrate host tissues while evading host defenses including enzyme secretion including hyaluronidase that can break down host tissues specially connective tissue, Variety disease like dermatitis, boils, impetigo, pneumonia, osteomyelitis, toxic shock syndrome and septicemia caused by *S. aureus* (Mastoor et al., 2022; Linz et al., 2023). The maximum production of yellow pigment by *Staphylococcus aureus* is obtained at temperature close to 30 °C. Pigment production in *Staphylococci* is strongly pH-dependent, with a different stereotypical range for each species, the organism *Staphylococcus saprophyticus* is produce maximum pigment at a neutral (pH 7.0) (Kim et al., 2010). Beside environmental conditions, nutrient availability is also an important factor for pigment formation in *Staphylococcus* spp. The amount and the kind of carbon sources, type and availability of nitrogen sources or presence of some

specific mineral ions could significantly influence both the yield and quality of pigment (López et al., 2021).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a Gram-negative opportunism, spore forming, motile by flagella and an obligate aerobic bacterium that grows well in a range of culture mediums, It grape-like odor. Some strains are beta hemolysis, *P. aeruginosa* is isolated and diagnosed using traditional bacterial growth culture and morphological characteristics, it's one of the most pollutants in hospital environments (Alqaissy et al., 2020). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* colonies are smooth and spherical, with a light green tint, these bacteria have ability to secrete substances spontaneously through their growth which distinguishes from other line, Many strains can produce pyocyanin, a blue pigment that diffuses in agar, It also creates a fluorescent pigment, which, when coupled with pyocyanin, gives the agar its green hue. Some strains generate red pigments (pyorubin), whereas others produce brownish-black pigments (pyomelanin) (Juan et al., 2017). *P. aeruginosa* isolates. Three types of colonies exist. Small, rough colonies are usually natural isolates from soil or water, but large, smooth colonies with flat edges and elevated appearances might be clinical isolates. These clinical colonies might have a fried egg appearance (Pérez et al., 2019). Infections with *P. aeruginosa* only arise when it reaches places with no natural defenses, such as when mucosal membranes and skin are injured by direct tissue injury, as in wounds and burns; when intravenous or urinary catheters are used; or when neutropenia is common, such in cancer therapy. The bacteria adhere to and colonize mucosal membranes or skin, then penetrate locally, causing systemic problems such as bloodstream infections (Kostylev et al., 2019). The pathogenicity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is determined by a variety of virulence factors, such as proteases, exotoxins, and phenazine pigments, many of which are regulated through quorum-sensing (QS) signaling in a cell density-dependent manner (Venil et al., 2020). This opportunistic human pathogen is highly prevalent in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, where it can cause severe diseases, like *P. aeruginosa*, particularly under immunocompromised conditions, otitis media or externa and osteomyelitis as a result simple puncture wounds, it enable to cause more complications like cranial neuropathies with acute skull base osteomyelitis additional wide spectrum from arrangement community acquired infections, these bacteria a highly resistant to all antibiotics and resistance and resist host defenses comparatively and thus due to it possess mutable mechanisms like make beta lactamase, biofilm, flux system that help it but the best mechanism of *P. aeruginosa* is the production of the soluble pigment known as pyocyanin (Srivastava et al., 2022).

Serratia marcescens

Serratia marcescens: are Gram negative rods structure a member of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, is one of the types of opportunistic pathogen mainly affecting patients, this bacteria has been isolated from catheters, oxygenation instruments, needles, parenteral solutions, nails and disinfectant solutions, this is due to ability to adapt and survive in most difficult conditions (Allen et al., 2022) this bacteria play important role in remarkable nosocomial infections, it causing infection such as urinary tract infections, respiratory tract infections, endocarditis and wounds infection in addition is one the common causes of bacteremia and pneumonia among gram negative also It is a major problem in healthcare settings, increase the infections process mediated by various virulence factors included secreted protease enzyme, hemolysins and lipopolysaccharides, it can be tract numbers of genetic factors like chromosomal encoded porins and efflux pump, but the more virulence factors effective in *Serratia marcescens* and they often are capsulated, this capsule reinforcement ability to biofilms formation which are the biofilms that are highly resistant to antimicrobial and lead to a aggravate of the bacterial infection and strengthen resistance to antibiotics (Khatoon et al., 2018; Lila et al., 2023).

Chromobacterium violaceum

Chromobacterium violaceum is a saprophytic facultative anaerobic, Gram-negative oxidase positive bacterium. It is temperature-dependent and prevalent in freshwater, as well as soil ecology especially within the

worms found in tropical and subtropical areas. Human infections are rare, however, when humans do become infected a high mortality rate results from the disease. Local abscesses can result from the bacterium, which may also spread through the bloodstream, causing septicemia, multiorgan failure, septic shock and death (Thwe et al., 2020). This organism is a tropical pathogen and an occasional invader of humans; its lethal infectivity in buffalo was first documented by Woolley (Alisjahbana et al., 202) in 1905. It is usually transmitted through ingestion of contaminated water, contact with soil or contact wounds or open skin lesions exposed to contaminated soil or water, and nosocomial routes following procedures using unsterilized instruments (i.e., urinary catheterization) and other hospital-acquired exposure (Sharmin et al., 2019). *C. violaceum* is usually resistant to many antimicrobials but sensitive to imipenem, gentamicin, tetracycline and especially ciprofloxacin which is considered the most effective treatment including norfloxacin and pefloxacin (Nayyar et al., 2019). It is a motile bacterium and bears a single polar flagellum and additional lateral flagella, with several pili that in essence aid in the bacterial motility (Ravichandran et al., 2018). *C. violaceum* is known for its ability to synthesize the pigment violacein, which imparts a characteristic dark purple-black colour on infected host tissue. In the past, violacein production and its dynamics in nanoparticulate environment have been the subject of concise investigation for an innovative approach to resist chronic bacterial infections, multidrug resistance, and their associated clinical complications (Usmani et al., 2020).

Advantages of Microbial Pigment

Bacteria are known as an economical biological chassis for pigment production, quick cell growth rate, diverse strains and relatively easy cultivation process. Moreover, bacterial hosts provide ease of downstream processing and a cost-effective replacement for current sources. Recently, using such recombinant DNA techniques developed, the production ability of natural pigments by bacterial hosts has been further improved and excessive lab-or field-scale plant cultivation is no longer required. As a result, pigments could be produced via microbial fermentation as feasible and 'green' alternative (Wang et al., 2021). Infection diseases are still one of the most responsible causes for death on world an urgent demand for strategies to combat these processes. Antioxidants are important in biological systems owing to their ability to donate electrons and scavenge free radicals, protecting the cell from oxidative stress-induced damage and help preserve cellular function (Celedón & Díaz, 2021). Microbial pigments also play a role as anticancer agents. A new red pigment from *Athrobacter sp.* showed anticancer activity against oesophageal cancer cell line Pigments with potential health and nutritional benefit are considered highly valuable and have a huge demand which is dominated by food industries. Consequently, there is a need to identify alternative sources of natural and safe food colorants (Silva et al., 2021). Pigment synthesis is one of the strategies that affords some microbes survival and adaptive advantages in stressed environments (Abdelaziz et al., 202). Microbial pigment production has the advantages of easy culturing and choosing from a wide range of strains, technique availability, simple post-processing treatment, and reduced cost compared with natural pigments (Venil et al., 2020).

Types of Bacterial Pigment

Pyocyanins and Pyoverdines

Pyocyanin is a blue- green pigment which is biologically active and water soluble, produced by the majority of *P. aeruginosa* strains. This pigment is produced as a secondary metabolite of faeces-associated bacterial metabolism and its synthesis is affected by multiple environmental factors; including bacterial species diversity, nitrogen source, carbon source, incubation temperature, pH and some other chemicals (DeBritto et al., 2020). Pyocyanin has garnered a lot of attention because of its multiple uses in numerous fields including the medical, pharmaceutical, biosensor and microbial fuel cell domains (Rana et al., 2021).

In addition, pyocyanin is a critical virulence factor and a quorum-sensing signal molecule involved in more than one essential biological functions. Due to the amphiphilic nature, pyocyanin is able to interact with membranes of both prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells, which contribute to pathogenesis in *P. aeruginosa*. Besides its role in infection, this pigment has shown considerable biological activities such as anticancer, antifungal and antibacterial against several pathogens (Pena et al., 2019). Pyocyanins and pyoverdines is a biological pigments can produce by the genus *Pseudomonas* and the pathogenic potential it has gained great importance its used in many medical and technological applications both in vital and artificial (Little et al., 2018). It is known that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has many virulence factors and the production of biological pigments is one of the most important signs of its diagnosis and pathogenesis (Jabłońska et al., 2023). Pyocyanin it's the first phenazic compound discovered in the *P. aeruginosa*, in origin just a pigment secreted in selective culture media without any vital function exaction simply crossing biological membranes, it unstable color it change depending on type solvent, it take a blue when mixed with alkaloid solution while red in acidic (Gonçalves & Vasconcelos, 2021). The application of pigment as a control against more pathogens has shown pure drugs effects and found pathogenic relation between *P. aeruginosa* and their host organism involving cell damage as the result of pro-inflammatory effects and the release of an uncharged molecules (Mudaliar & Bharath Prasad, 2024). pyoverdine is other pigments secreted by *P.aeruginosa* that biogenesis start in cell cytoplasm when cultured on cetrimide agar bioluminescent greenish-yellow and iron connecting compound for iron conquest, this bioactive dye ,it supply fluorescent to psedomonadaceae and contributed to abnormal increase the virulence bacteria against competitor bacteria addition played pivotal role in prevent adherent bacteria from forming biofilms and were reported for its antagonistic activity against several multiple drugs resistant(MDR), its important in up regulate the transcription of confirmed elastases (Durán et al., 2022). King's A medium agar play a vital role by increasing the bacterial density and would produce maximal amounts of pyocyanin pigment, pyocyanin could be explored for use in topical treatments for wound infections and exacerbates the damaging effects of nosocomial infection and the colony features of *P.aeruginosa* effected by pyocyanin pigment during act a part of quorum-sensing (Zhu et al., 2019).

Prodigiosin

Prodigiosin is a red pigment secondary metabolite produced by a variety of bacterial species, the most prominent of these is *Serratia marcescens* its able to direct influence by actions on target bacteria out up DNA demolition, PH unstable, phototoxicity ,enzymes and cell membrane permeation as well as interaction with cell cycle by clawed on discrete cells components ,It was first extracted from *Serratia marcescens* ,its considered one of the distinctive morphological signs of *S. marcescens* the production of prodigiosin pigment at room temperature, the pigment makes the surface colony the bacteria are growth red in color, it was used as a platform to bring a family of molecules with diverse biological activities obtained by chemical synthesis (Kirienko et al., 2019). Pigment is low soluble in water but soluble in chemical compound like methanol, ethanol, hexane ,acetone, chloroform the structural characteristics of Pigment It is sensitive to light (Tariq et al., 2021). *Serratia marcescen* is an opportunistic pathogen capable of causing a wide range of infections, including those affecting the skin, respiratory tract, central nervous system (such as meningitis), as well as endocarditis, arthritis, and keratitis. One of the distinctive features of this bacterium is the production of a red pigment characterized by a pyrrolyl–pyromethene core structure. This pigment group includes several related compounds, such as prodigiosin, metacycloprodigiosin, and desmethoxyprodigiosin. These compounds have been reported to exhibit notable biological activities, particularly antimicrobial and antimalarial effects, with prodigiosin being the most extensively studied and biologically active among them (Ravindran et al., 2020). The first requirements for pigment isolation is to cultured *S. marcescen* on media including inorganic phosphate (Espona-Fiedler et al., 2022). Mechanism targets of PG interaction in biological systems are nucleic acid in particular in to the DNA helix and membrane components proteins and lipids, the normal of interaction depends on the presence of copper, zinc ions , its synthesis depends on many factors, such

as incubation time, pH, carbon and nitrogen sources, and inorganic salts (Amorim et al., 2022). The red pigment PG which can be used to replace synthetic dyes in the food sector and depicts the chemical structure of prodigiosin, which is notable for its ability to change color in response to pH variations, lending it wide-ranging applications (Köksal Karayildirim et al., 2024). Prodigiosin was first isolated from the bacterium *Serratia marcescens*, it is perhaps the most common microbial pigment because of its bright red color. It is known to have anti-malarial, antibacterial, antineoplastic, antibiotic activity and reported multiple pharmacological effects (Ahmed et al., 2021).

Violacein

Violacein is a small molecular weight bacteria violet or purple pigment produce mainly chramobacteria genus, there are several ways to synthesize violacein, such as using bacteria. This pigment can also be found in bacteria from different environments, first isolated from the Amazon River in Brazil, its soluble in alcohol but water in-soluble (Durán et al., 2021). Violacein is a naturally-occurring bacterial secondary metabolite which is known to demonstrate a wide range of biological properties including antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral as well as anticancer and antitumor activities (Kanelli et al., 2018). Violacein a good used in wound healing analgesic and antipyretic and when using combinations with antimicrobial properties is an attractive prospect for solving the health and environmental disorders (Atalah et al., 2020). In nature, violacein might be responsible for protection against UV radiation, violacein can be used to treat several diseases caused by fungi, parasites, Violacein associated with lipid carriers has shown toxicity capable of controlling cancer cell growth (Rivero-Berti et al., 2020). its synthesis occurs through quorum sensing mechanisms, meticulously assess pigment production in the presence of nanoparticles, offering novel approaches to combat bacterial persistent infections and counter multidrug resistance and the associated challenges (Anahas et al., 2022). These pigment have better stability at PH 5-9 on temperature about (77-212 F) with presence of light metal ion and H₂O₂ (Pauer et al., 2018). The great importance adaptive response of bacterial communities to the environment occur by coordinated metabolic arrangements produced by qualitative particles named quorum signs and this linked with pigment by up regulated biofilm of life (Batista & da Silva Neto, 2017). Violacein production rate was increased using brown sugar, molasses, sugarcane bagasse, and pineapple waste, Violacein had also strongly inhibited the formation of *S. aureus* biofilm but had no effect against mature biofilm (López et al., 2021).

Staphyloxanthin

Staphyloxanthin is a carotenoid pigment found in *Staphylococcus aureus*, Structurally the cell wall of *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria contains lipids, the bacteria have the ability to convert these lipids into environmentally friendly substances, transforming them into substances that resist oxidation, osmotic pressure, and anti-pathogen factors (Cheung et al., 2021). Staphyloxanthin is an orange-ish membrane bound carotenoid pigment that appears to contribute to the characteristic golden color of *S. aureus* cells. This pigment is essential for bacterial physiology and has been two important roles inside the cell; a protective role during oxidative stress by scavenging ROS and, it stabilizes and maintains the integrity of bacterial cell wall against harsh environments (Aruldass et al., 2018). The synthesis of staphyloxanthin by *S. aureus* is an effective virulence factor between a group of virulence factors possessed by bacteria a site closely connected to the activates of antioxidant resistant this has greatly contributed to resistance of bacteria to the antibiotics and phagocytic process (Ribeiro et al., 2018). Staphyloxanthin production is regarded as a significant virulence factor of *S. aureus*, alongside various other factors including enzymes such as coagulase, catalase, lipase, protease, DNase, hyaluronidase, beta-lactamase, as well as toxins such as toxic shock syndrome toxin. Additionally, *S. aureus* virulence encompasses biofilm formation, immunoinvasive strategies, and antibiotic resistance (Xue et al., 2019). Controlling the biosynthesis of staphyloxanthin, the yellow pigment in *Staphylococcus aureus*, is viewed as a promising approach since it could decrease bacterial survival upon infection and increase susceptibility to host immune responses. Carotenoid pigments are critical factors protecting *S. aureus* from oxidative and immune system attack,

being relevant to its virulence. Among them, numerous compounds and strategies have been developed that selectively disturb staphyloxanthin synthesis by inhibiting key enzymes of the biosynthesis pathway such as dehydrosqualene synthase (CrtM) and catalytic desaturase (CrtN) (Múnera-Jaramillo et al., 2024).

Table 1. Major Bacterial Pigments, Their Discoverers, Biological Colors, and Therapeutic Activities

N	Bacteria	Pigment	Scientist discoverer	Year discovery	Pigment color	Effect
1	<i>S. aureus</i>	Staphyloxanthin	Alexander ogston	1880	Yellow	Anticancer Antioxidant
2	<i>S. marcescens</i>	Prodigiosin	Craft	1902	Red	Anticancer DNA cleavage Immunosuppres
3	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	Pyocyanins	Ford	1860	Blue	Cytotoxicity Neutrophil Apoptosis Ciliary dismotility Pro inflammatory
4	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	pyoverdines	Gessard	1892	Greenish-yellow	Recycling of siderophore and iron acquisition
5	<i>C. violaceum</i>	Violacein	Boisbaudran	1882	Purple	Antifungal Antibacterial Antiplasmodial

Applications of Pigmented Bacteria

In recent years as a result of the huge explosion in the field of biotechnology which has penetrated all aspects of life ,this has led to an expansion in the development and use of bacteriological pigments due to their benefits and current returns in various area of the life in general and biotechnology ,medicine and pharmacology in particular and this a main reason for the boom in the use bacterial pigments global market (Venil et al., 2020). One major industrial application of bacterial pigments is unrelated to their visual characteristics. Certain bacterial pigments are utilized for their health-promoting properties, as they provide essential nutrients and bioactive compounds required by the human body.

Bacterial Pigments in Medical Biotechnology

Medical biotechnology is an indispensable tool to meet current threats against human health such as increasing incidence of cancer, formation of superbug microbes, and growing number of multi-drug resistant incurable infections. Bacterial pigments have generated interest based on their remarkable biological activities, which include antitumor, anticancer, and antiviral properties (Elmesseri et al., 2022). Some examples are the potential use of violacein in interacting with venture particles and *Bdellovibrio bacteriovorus* to control colonisation between cells in mixed communities, inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Im et al., 2017). In addition, violacein has been described as an inhibitor of various cancer cells including breast cancer cells (Alem et al., 2020). Prodigiosins have been found in actinomycetes from marine sponges. These pigments also possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, therefore they are considered to be potential therapeutic candidates for the prevention of gastric injury, as well as potential substitutes for traditional anti-ulcer drugs like omeprazole (Abdelfattah et al., 201). *Streptomyces sp.* and *Zoosbigella sp.* exhibits significant antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Ramesh et al., 2020).

Food Industry

The visual aspect of food products has a significant importance in the food industries. The natural colors are often added to various products such as Dairy, Canned fruits, Jams, confectionery and beverages in order to visually improve the appearance of these products. In the past few years, food producers have been moving more and more towards natural colorants in lieu of synthetic additives, microbial pigments play a vital role in food fermentation, offering a superior alternative to synthetic food colorants and plant-based pigments (Sen et al., 2019). Microbial pigments may be climacteric compounds, when compared between the bacterial dye with artificial the bacterial dye is a pattern alternative to synthetic food colors because it has several components constituents such as availability and capacity addition it is known that artificial food coloring are produced from petroleum wastes (Weiss et al., 2023). Microbially derived carotenoid pigments represent a growing commercial sector, as they improve the organoleptic properties of food products without compromising quality. In addition, these compounds are associated with health-related benefits, including antioxidant activity that may contribute to disease prevention and cellular protection (Nabi et al., 2023). Solubility of the microbial pigment leading to better delivery systems for food, and feed, microbial pigments can be either inorganic or organic, although organic pigments tend to be more useful as food colorants (Orlandi et al., 2022).

Pharmaceutical and Medicine

Pharmaceutical industries mostly used the bacterial pigments substitution in incurable disease such as malignant tumor, microbial disease, leishmaniasis, immunosuppressive disorders and other, this is due to possession of numbers of specific therapeutic components like flavonoids, quinols and steroids and pigments are safe for human and preserve biodiversity (Sen et al., 2019). Bacteria pigments have many antioxidant properties, ability to regulate the apoptosis of the cells additional can benefit in pharmaceutical formulations increase the safety of formulations and especially the shelf lives of the almost perishable products (Dos Santos et al., 2018). The successful utilization of bacteria that produce biologically active secondary metabolites depends on the feasibility of cost-effective production and the broad range of potential applications in the pharmacological field (Tunca Koyun et al., 2022; Nawaz et al., 2021; Durán et al., 2022). The unconstrained use of drugs mainly antibiotics in the all communities even those of a civilized nature has arisen in the emergence of resistant strains that continue to grow and become a real problem with remarkable development basis, in same time bacterial resistance can also enhance to numerous types of antibiotics named as multidrug resistance, it is necessary used a new antibiotics extracted from marine bacteria to treat bacterial diseases (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2019). Bacterial pigments represent a promising group of compounds with diverse pharmacological properties (Karbalaei-Heidari et al., 2020; Ghattavi et al., 2022). Antimicrobial, anticancer, and antioxidant properties of bacterial pigments make them popular in drug industries. Owing to the medicinal properties of bacterial pigments they were considered as the best choice for novel drugs (Numan et al., 2018).

Bioremediation

Environmental pollution most important problem facing the entire world as a result of massive population growth and fast industrialization addition climate change, ecological degradation manure to soil and disinfectants main factors to environmental pollution and this influential directly on human health (Sharma et al., 2022). Bioremediation is a process primarily including of degradation, detoxification and transformation of the pollutants such as pigments, heavy metal, pigments waste water, sewage and gases by safety methods (Swapnil et al., 2023). Cyanobacteria, fungi, yeasts and microbial consortiums have more potential to get rid of pollutants by acting as toxic pollutant biosorbents (Tripathi & Singh, 2022). Marine biofouling as a result from dreadnoughts which used fuel and waste disposal to seawater has become a prominent threat for the maritime environment, some toxic phytoplankton can cause algal blooms and this leads to marine biofouling and the Prodigiosin pigment produced by proteobacterium

or marine bacteria strain display potent algicidal activity against red tide phytoplankton (Garg & Chopra, 2022; Kim et al., 2008). Conformation pigmented bacteria can avail as bioindicator to environmental health example the carotenoid can assistance the level environmental pollution as well as Some carotenoids, combined with plant growth-promoting substances, can help plants withstand environmental stress (Sharma et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Bacterial pigments are promising ecofriendly antimicrobial agents with unique inhibition mechanisms against resistant pathogens. Their pharmaceutical and industrial applications may support future strategies to combat antimicrobial resistance effectively.

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